

Celebrating 1 year of Rural BioReFarmeries

Dear reader,

On 1st December 2024, we embarked on a 4-year-long journey to demonstrate how small-scale, decentralised green biorefineries can make a positive impact in rural Europe while helping to drive a robust bioeconomy. I'm very proud to say we're already one year in and we're seeing fantastic progress in our project.

We've started to scale technologies from bench up to pilot in Ireland and Denmark, and up to demonstration scale in Denmark as well. We have also seen the first prototype products developed by our different work packages, including fibre-based packaging produced from grass press, and white protein materials which will be further tested.

These achievements are thanks to the efforts made by all the partners in the RBRF consortium; I've been inspired by the way they have all tackled their tasks collaboratively from the very beginning of the project, embodying a true multidisciplinary spirit defined their commitment towards advancing sustainable and circular bio-based solutions in Europe.

I invite you to read through, and celebrate with us all the milestones achieved during this first year working together. As the holiday season begins, we will take these next few weeks to reflect and prepare for what's ahead in 2026!

James Gaffey — Rural BioReFarmeries Project Coordinator.

[Learn more about our progress](#)

Understand our mission

The aim of Rural BioReFarmeries is to demonstrate how Europe's vast grasslands can become the gateway to build a true circular bioeconomy. But what does this mean in practical terms? We have created a short film to explain the whole mission of RBRF... in just under 3 minutes!

[Watch the video](#)

Our top story in this edition

Celebrating the first year of the project in Rome

The [Rural BioReFarmeries consortium](#) gathered in Rome on 4-5 December 2025 for its end-of-year General Assembly, hosted by the team from Unitelma Sapienza in their premises at the heart of the eternal city.

The meeting, which also coincided with the official first anniversary of the project, brought together over 40 representatives from the [19 RBRF partners](#) to reflect on the progress achieved during the first 12 months, and to define the key objectives for 2026.

[Watch the video](#) featuring highlights shared by some partners, and [read this article](#) to learn how the results achieved so far will shape upcoming tasks across all work packages.

A closer look

The team from [ACRRES at Wageningen University & Research \(WUR\)](#) in The Netherlands have been working with [PaperFoam](#) to **develop the first prototypes of bio-based packaging made out of grass fibres**, which were provided by our Danish partners from Aarhus University after harvesting and biorefining the grass at their [pilot facilities in AU Viborg](#).

During the latest General Assembly in Rome, [Rommié van der Weide and Matthew Booth from WUR](#) got to showcase these initial materials with the rest of the partners in the room, and explained that different treatments produce a variety of results in terms of colours and textures. **Check them out below!**

[Find out more](#)

In conversation with RBRF experts

Aliabbas Saleh

Carbery

On building a business case to bring grass-based high-protein products from the lab to the consumers.

[Read the interview](#)

Claus Gron Sorensen

Aarhus University

On how to optimise biomass supply chains and improve the adoption of smart farming technologies.

[Read the interview](#)

Liz Gavin

NuaFund

On the changing landscape of EU-funding research and innovation, and the pivot towards bioeconomy efforts.

[Read the interview](#)

Andreas Gravholt

SEGES Innovation

On how to work closely with farmers to replicate green biorefinery technologies effectively across Europe.

[Read the interview](#)

In other news

RBRF spotlighted by Horizon Europe Ireland

Ireland's National Support Network for Horizon Europe put the spotlight on Rural BioReFarmeries' potential to boost rural economies and the EU's bioeconomy.

New collaboration with NUTRI-CHECK NET

We have started exploring joint efforts with this EU-funded initiative, which aims to improve the precision of crop nutrition across fields in Europe.

RBRF showcased at Irish Bioeconomy Forum

Researchers from MTU's CBIO presented the mission of RBRF and the demo-scale work on Farm Zero C at this multi-stakeholder event in Ireland.

[Get more details](#)

RBRF recommended reads

A selection of the latest reports, research articles and opinion pieces about the bioeconomy and the current state of bio-based innovation.

- ◆ [*Towards efficient grass-clover biorefining: Influence of harvesting methods and delayed processing*](#) - research paper by GO-GRASS project partners
- ◆ [*Achieving Leadership in the Global Bioeconomy*](#) - article published on Agro & Chemistry in collaboration with Bio-based Industries Consortium (BIC)
- ◆ [*Sustainability assessments of bio-based products: From research to practice \(and standards\)*](#) - research paper by STAR-ProBio project partners
- ◆ [*Circular bioeconomy: What it means and how to get there*](#) - report by UN Trade and Development (UNCTAD)
- ◆ [*A life cycle thinking-based environmental risk framework for screening sustainable feedstocks in early-stage bioeconomy projects*](#) - research paper by INFORMBIO project partners
- ◆ [*Benefits of Using First-Generation Biomass for Food, Fuels, Chemicals and Derived Materials in Europe*](#) - report by Renewable Carbon Initiative, commissioned by the European Bioeconomy Alliance
- ◆ [*State-of-the-art in assessing the environmental performance of anaerobic digestion biorefineries*](#) - research paper by RBRF partner Vincent O'Flaherty from University of Galway

Follow our journey! 🌱🐜

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